

HYBRID GLASS-FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Thermoplastic montmorillonite-based nanocomposites show significant property improvements with respect to unmodified polymers, including increased dimensional stability, heat distortion temperature, stiffness, strength, and flame retardance. The use of nano-sized fillers also offers far greater versatility in terms of processing than conventional fillers, although they may significantly increase the melt viscosity at low concentrations, with potentially adverse consequences for processing. In the present work, the feasibility of integrating thermoplastic polypropylene nanocomposite matrices into conventional fibre-reinforced composites has been investigated. Two basic processing routes were considered: long glass fibre-reinforced composites based on co-woven yarns, and glass mat reinforced composites. In each case satisfactory impregnation and consolidation were demonstrated and flexural tests on the glass mat reinforced composites indicated use of a nanocomposite matrix to lead to significant stiffness improvements for a given glass fibre content.

KEYWORDS: melt spinning, fibres, films, textiles, nanocomposites, glass mat thermoplastics.

INTRODUCTION

Combining polymer matrices with inorganic fillers, such as exfoliated montmorillonite (MMT) clay, characterized by at least one dimension in the nanometre size range size, has the potential not only to improve their performance but also to broaden their range of functionality. The resulting “nanocomposites” are hence of considerable interest as matrices for fibre-reinforced composites, particularly because the use of reduced filler sizes is expected to limit the segregation effects observed when attempts are made to infiltrate fibre beds with polymers containing conventional fillers. Improved matrix performance is expected to lead to improvements in the final composite parts, increasing their competitiveness with traditional alternatives. Nanocomposite technology may also allow replacement of more expensive technical polymers by commodity polymers such as isotactic polypropylene (PP) in applications with relatively stringent performance criteria. However, for high volume applications typical of the automotive industry, for example, any such new composite materials must also be cost effective in terms of processing [1]. Property improvements reported for thermoplastic MMT-based nanocomposites, include increased dimensional stability, heat distortion temperature, stiffness, strength and flame retardance [2], although the presence of highly exfoliated MMT in thermoplastic matrices may result in significant increases in melt viscosity, even at low concentrations, with potentially adverse consequences

for many types of processing. High degrees of exfoliation and dispersion may also be difficult to obtain, depending on the compatibility of the MMT and the matrix. There has consequently been a concerted effort to improve control of MMT dispersions in a wide range of matrices, generally involving modification of the MMT with an organic surfactant. In the case of PP, bulk organically modified MMT/PP precursors are now available commercially at competitive prices, so that the feasibility and benefits of integrating thermoplastic nanocomposite matrices into fibre-reinforced composites are of immediate industrial interest. In the present work, two processing routes for hybrid nanocomposite fibre-reinforced composites are considered: long glass fibre-reinforced composites based on co-woven yarns, as a step towards the fabrication of nanocomposite-based co-mingled yarns [3] glass mat reinforced thermoplastic (GMT) composites [4].

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials processing

PP/MMT nanocomposite granulates were prepared by melt compounding PP homopolymer with a melt flow index (MFI) of 3.7g/min, designed for fibre applications (Borealis), and a commercial PP/40-50 wt% organically modified MMT concentrate (Nanocor) at 200 °C using a Prism twin-screw extruder. Melt spun PP/MMT fibres were prepared from the nanocomposites using a Fourné Polymertechnik GmbH Laboratory Melt-Spintester equipped with a single-screw extruder and a spinneret containing 36 circular dies of 0.4 mm in diameter. The temperatures in successive zones of the extruder from the entrance to the spinneret were set to 210 °C, 245 °C and 245 °C, respectively, and the pressure at the gear pump was 7 MPa. Precursor fabrics were prepared by co-weaving as-spun PP/MMT yarns with glass fibre (GF) yarns (Roving EC 17, 1200 Tex from Glasseide-Oschatz GmbH) or with poly (ether ether ketone) (PEEK) yarns (Zytex type Z3110). The co-woven yarns were typically compression moulded at 1.2 MPa for 10 min at 220 °C to produce the final consolidated parts. PP/MMT films of nominally 1 mm thickness were produced by extrusion through a planar die at 180°C and 40 rpm from PP/MMT granulates produced as described above. Model consolidated GMT plaques were obtained by sandwiching two 2D needled planar random glass fibre mats with three PP/MMT extruded films and placing the resulting stack in a closed 120 mm × 50 mm mould. The assembly was then heated to typically 200 °C for 10 min at a constant pressure of 2 MPa, maintained at 200 °C for a further 10 min, and then rapidly cooled. This gave a fibre mass fraction in the resulting GMT of 30%.

Characterization

Rheological measurements on the as-compounded nanocomposite extrudates were performed with either a Rheometrics ARES in steady state or oscillating shear (strains up to 0.5 %) using the cone-plate geometry, or a twin-bore Rosand RH7 capillary rheometer in shear flow. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) temperature sweeps at a rate 2 Kmin⁻¹ and different constant frequencies were obtained using a rheometrics RSA II. Injection moulded bars of the nanocomposites were tested in three-point bending, whereas the fibres (27 mm gage length) and films (27 mm gage length, specimen width 2 mm) were tested in tension. The static tensile properties of the PP nanocomposite yarns were measured using a miniature materials tester (MiniMat 2000 from Rheometrics Scientific equipped with a 20 N load cell). The gauge length was between 10 mm and 20 mm and testing was carried out according to DIN 53 834, with a preload of 0.5 cN/Tex. Static three-point bend tests were carried out at room temperature, 50 °C and 90 °C at a constant crosshead speed of 1.2 mm/min on 2.2 mm x 25

mm x 60 mm bars machined from the moulded GMT plaques, using a UTS Testsystem GmbH. The flexural data referred to later corresponded to mean values from a minimum of 6 tests. The state of dispersion of the MMT was investigated by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) (Philips EM430 operated at 300 kV) of RuO₄-stained ultramicrotomed sections of about 50 to 100 nm in thickness, and by wide-angle X-ray diffraction (WAXS) in reflection mode.

Fig. 1: η vs. shear rate at 220 °C for different MMT contents: (a) cone-plate measurements; (b) capillary rheometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PP/MMT melt response

The flow behaviour of melt compounded nanocomposites was investigated principally in order to (i) determine whether established processing windows for PP film extrusion and fibre spinning require modification in the presence of MMT and (ii) to gain an idea of the extent to which impregnation of the composite fibre beds is likely to be affected by the MMT. The steady state shear viscosity, η , shown in Fig. 1 as a function of shear rate, was seen to increase strongly with MMT content at low shear rates. However, increasingly pronounced shear thinning was observed as the MMT content increased, so that its influence was markedly reduced at shear rates above about 1 s^{-1} . It may therefore be inferred that the effective η associated with film extrusion and fibre spinning (typical strain rates in the range 10 to 2000 s^{-1}) remains close to that of the unmodified PP, requiring no major modification in process conditions. Other important limitations on spinnability include (i) melt fracture [5], which is linked to distortions in the extrusion die that result from pressure instabilities, leading to the break-up of the molten fibre into droplets, and (ii) rupture of fibres during subsequent roll-up, which may be critical in cases where there is insufficient relaxation of stresses induced during

drawing [6]. The evolution of the pressure drop with shear rate on passing the melt through a capillary die [7], shown in Fig. 2a, reflected the nonlinear behaviour associated with high shear rates. However, the behaviour was only weakly dependent on MMT content, and there was no evidence for melt fracture. Fig. 2b gives the results of melt relaxation measurements in terms of a relaxation time constant corresponding to a 63 % decrease in pressure with respect to its initial value after cessation of shear [8]. The time constants obtained in this way increased systematically with MMT content, and it may hence be inferred that beyond some limiting MMT concentration, the relaxation rate will diminish to the point where the drawing stress becomes sufficient to break the fibres.

Fig. 2: (a) Melt pressure drop at the entrance of the capillary die as a function of shear rate for different MMT contents; (b) relaxation times as a function of MMT content.

Fig. 3: Maximum drive-roll velocity for fibre spinning of PP with different MMT contents

Experimentally, the most severe restrictions on the MMT content were indeed linked to the tendency for the nanocomposites to undergo catastrophic failure during drawing. However, this was also thought to have been due to weak spots associated with local inhomogeneity in the clay dispersion, as reflected by increasingly non-uniform fibre cross-sections as the MMT content was raised. Adequate pre-mixing of the nanocomposite was therefore essential for the successful production of uniform fibres. Even so, the maximum MMT content at which the fibres could be spun and drawn under the present conditions was only about 7.5 wt%. Fibres

could be melt spun at higher MMT contents, but the maximum drive-roll velocity and hence the extent to which the fibres could be drawn was severely limited, as shown in Fig. 3. Because it did not involve a drawing step, film extrusion was not limited by the MMT content within the range investigated in the present study. However, the quality and homogeneity of the films was again strongly dependent on the quality of pre-mixing of the nanocomposite precursor.

Fig. 4: TEM micrographs of the as-compounded PP/MMT nanocomposites: (a) 6 wt% MMT; (b) 10 wt% MMT.

Precursor morphologies and properties

Fig. 4 shows representative TEM images of as-compounded nanocomposite extrudates with nominal MMT contents of 6 and 10 wt%, in which the MMT was considered to be well dispersed. Exfoliation was nevertheless incomplete and many of the MMT particles consisted of stacks of individual MMT layers rather than isolated layers, as reported elsewhere for similar materials [9]. The TEM image of a longitudinal section through a drawn PP/6 wt% MMT fibre shown in Fig. 5 indicates that the MMT stacks were fully aligned with the fibre axis, and the PP lamellae were oriented perpendicular to the planes of the stacks. Sections taken perpendicular to the fibre axis, on the other hand, suggested relatively little organization perpendicular to the flow direction (Fig. 5b), consistent with previous observations [9]. WAXS also indicated an increase in the MMT layer spacing in the stacks by up to 35 % in the PP/MMT fibres over that in the as-received organo-MMT concentrate, suggesting substantial additional intercalation of the PP chains. The degree of MMT orientation in the fibres was sensitive to the roll-up speed and un-drawn fibres showed more limited orientation of both the MMT stacks and the PP lamellae than the drawn fibres. Orientation was also limited in the extruded films, with degrees of alignment in longitudinal sections comparable to those seen in the un-drawn fibres, again consistent with previous observations [10, 11]. Moreover, only modest increases (around 6 %) in the MMT layer spacing were observed in the films. The concentration, degree of dispersion and orientation of the MMT layers are important for mechanical properties, as one would expect by analogy with conventional composites [12]. Thus the reinforcing effect of the MMT on the axial stiffness, as inferred from both static tests and DMA measurements, was generally greater in the drawn fibres (increase in modulus by a factor of approximately 2 at room temperature for 6 wt% MMT) than in the un-drawn fibres or extrudates, in which the MMT layers showed less orientation (a factor of approximately 1.4

in modulus at room temperature for 6 wt% MMT). However, given that the contributions from both the matrix and the MMT to the axial stiffness of the fibres depend on the draw ratio [13], any decrease in drawability of the fibres in the presence of the MMT will severely limit the maximum stiffness that can be obtained at high MMT contents. In the present context, this is not a major issue, because for reasons of dimensional stability, highly drawn fibres may not be suitable for composite applications involving subsequent thermoforming operations, and indeed only un-drawn fibres were employed in the co-woven yarns referred to below. On the other hand, if the properties of the fibres themselves are to be optimized with respect to the processing conditions, it implies a corresponding optimum MMT content, which in the present case was estimated from static modulus measurements to be about 1 wt%.

Fig. 5: TEM micrographs of drawn fibres (6 wt% MMT, draw ratio 1, roll-up speed 1080m/min): (a) longitudinal section; (b) transverse section.

Fig. 6: Micrographs of transverse sections from co-woven hybrid nanocomposite yarns compression moulded at 220 °C and 1.2 MPa: (a) optical micrograph of a PP/6 wt% MMT/GF composite; (b) TEM of a PP/6 wt% MMT/PEEK composite.

Fig. 7: (a) Glass mat reinforced PP/MMT nanocomposite and glass mat reinforced neat PP (right hand specimen) compression moulded at 200 °C and 2 MPa (a); optical micrograph of a transverse section through a glass mat reinforced PP/6 wt% MMT nanocomposite.

Fig. 8: (a) Flexural strength and (b) flexural modulus of GMT-based composites for different MMT contents and temperatures, normalized with respect to the room temperature values for the un-modified matrix (nominal glass mass fraction of 30%).

Hybrid glass fibre reinforced nanocomposites

A transverse section from a co-woven GF/nanocomposite yarn compression moulded at 220 °C is shown Fig. 6a, indicating good impregnation and a relatively uniform GF distribution. The TEM micrograph in Fig. 6b, in which the GF was replaced by PEEK in order to facilitate sectioning, shows the MMT stacks to infiltrate the reinforcing fibre bundles, and sections taken perpendicular and parallel to the fibre direction confirmed the MMT to have lost any orientation acquired during spinning. Typical GMT composites obtained by moulding at 200 °C are shown in Fig. 7. Good impregnation of the fibre bed and minimal porosity were again achieved under these conditions. However, at the highest MMT contents (10 wt%), an approximately 3-fold increase in moulding times at constant temperature and pressure was required in order to obtain comparable degrees of porosity (between 1 and 2 %) to those obtained with the unmodified matrix. This presumably reflects the observed increase in η with MMT in the nanocomposites at low flow rates (Fig. 2b) and indeed impregnation times at constant pressure are expected to increase linearly with η for Newtonian matrices [14]. Nevertheless, as shown in Fig. 8, in cases where satisfactory consolidation was achieved, the observed improvements in stiffness of the nanocomposite precursors were reflected by corresponding strength and stiffness improvements in the GMT specimens (a roughly 25% increase in stiffness for a matrix content of 6 wt% MMT).

CONCLUSIONS

PP/MMT nanocomposites were successfully using conventional thermoforming techniques to produce films and fibres suitable for further composite processing techniques. Ideal exfoliated microstructures were not achieved, but the presence of MMT in relatively low concentrations nevertheless led to significant improvements in the mechanical properties of the precursors. Glass reinforced nanocomposites could be prepared by compression moulding of either co-woven GF-PP/MMT yarns or PP/MMT films interspersed with glass mats. Comparable degrees of consolidation were achieved to those in glass reinforced PP, although it was necessary to increase the moulding time and/or pressure somewhat in the glass mat reinforced composites, consistent with the observed increases in viscosity in the presence of MMT at low flow rates. Mechanical tests on the glass mat reinforced composites confirmed the MMT to lead to significant improvements in their overall stiffness and strength. The co-woven composites are considered an intermediate step pending future commingled trials that will reduce the mass transfer distance during impregnation (Darcy's law) and hence reduce impregnation times. Based on the present results this is expected to be a crucial consideration for the implementation of nanocomposite matrices.

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